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KANGLA LANPUNG

SUMMER 2022

VOLUME XIV ISSUE I

ISSN (Print): 2321-2357

Published by:

RK Sanatomba Memorial Trust,
Palace Compound, Manipur

Manipuri Nationalism and the Barak Valley march of 1993: A preliminary study

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This article is an excerpt from our forthcoming book on the same topic.

In 1993- 1994, dozens of Meitei youths, aged between fifteen and thirty-five, were shot dead by unknown assailants on different occasions in the valley of Manipur. The killings occurred over a relatively short period of time and in close geographic proximity to each other. In addition, it appears that all the cases were deeply intertwined. These indicated some sort of a mass murder program, and the question remains whether someone or a group of interested people or certain entity strongly attempted to silence a vibrant new generation. It remains an enigma to all.

The Barak Valley March of 1993 was a crucial piece of the puzzle. About half of the victims were later identified as the volunteers who took part in this march. However, the history of Barak valley march has not yet been explicitly addressed and is often overlooked, or even self-censored by scholars. This study will, therefore, be the first to examine the key events leading up to this heinous case of mass assassination in Manipur's contemporary history.

In the winter of 1992, a single-page leaflet, was widely circulated in the Manipur valley. The leaflet was issued by the publicity team of a civil organisation called Manipuri National Federation (Manfederation being its acronym). The leaflet was published on December 24,

1992. The heading in Meiteirol reads “*Chahi Taret Khuntakpa Ningsing Tha, January 1993*”. It can be translated as “Join a month-long Commemoration of the Seven Years Genocide”. The leaflet ended with a rally cry:

*“Kangla lanpung yeire,
 Ima leibakna nangbu koure,
 Safi lanphi setkatlo,
 Leipak thougai pangnaba,
 Ekhunai sibu kannaba.”*

(Th’re sounds the war-drum in Kangla.¹
 ‘T is mine own country’s calleth,
 Weareth thy armour,
 To volunte'r in the s'rvic'e of thy country
 And to defend our nation.)
 (*Author’s translation*)

The same leaflet was also published in the journal *Kangla Lanpung* under a different heading, “Genocide Never Again”. The *Kangla Lanpung* was a monthly periodical published in Imphal. It was once the official organ of Manfederation from 1991 to 1993. The leaflet and circular called for self-determination, including the consolidation of the Meiteis, and reads,

“Eikhoi Amuk Khuntaklaroi”
 (Genocide Never Again)

“The United Nations have declared 1993 to be the year of the World’s Indigenous People. Related to this, several indigenous communities all over the world, and especially belonging to Southeast Asia, Africa, North and South America, who have their own chequered history of an indigenously developed cultural and traditional way of life and self-rule have been subjected to colonial repression and administration; in response, at this critical juncture, several resistance movements are being waged sans stop by these communities to safeguard their identity and independent existence which is on the verge of extinction under colonial pressure.

¹Kangla was once the seat of the Manipuri kingdom.

In Manipur, another colonised nation in South-east Asia, where the indigenous people have completely forgotten the taste of freedom, the UN's declaration is warmly welcomed. Bringing together the global movement of self-determination and the history of our liberation movement, we will observe a month-long commemoration called *Chahi Taret Khuntakpa ningsingtha* in January 1993. With this memorial, we hope the lessons that were learned during that extraordinary and dark period of our nation's history will not be forgotten. We must instead keep this chapter in our collective consciences as a stark reminder of what we can do in a conflict, and what we should not repeat.

The disintegration of Manipur began with the forced conversion of the Meiteis into an alien religion [in the 18th century], thus creating a barrier between the hill people and the valley Meiteis. Moreover, the numerous succession crises plagued Manipur.

The Meitei princes threw themselves under the knees of their enemy, the Burmese emperor, and pleaded for assistance. The Burmese, who had been waiting for a good opportunity to avenge their long suffering at the hands of the Meiteis in the past, took this opportunity to destroy Manipur. They launched a campaign of genocide, popularly known in our history as "*Chahi Taret Khuntakpa*". Innocent people paid the price. Countless women were attacked and raped. Many innocents were forced into slavery. Children were killed by slamming into flagstone slabs. Several were killed by the smoke from burning dry chillies in confined spaces.

When adverse times came, the Meitei princes fled to the Barak Valley rather than defending the country. They soon realised their mistake. They took on a leadership role in bringing together the Meiteis, who were scattered all over the Barak valley. After mobilizing 500 troops in the Barak Valley, they fought back against the Burmese and ended seven years of Burmese genocide. Our defeat was the result of our irreconcilable differences. If we are united, no power on earth can defeat us. We need to set aside our rivalry and win back our country. It has been proven by the history of our liberation movement.

After the World War II, the seeds of independence were sown all over the world. Under the leadership of their national liberation movements, many nations, however, are still fighting for freedom and independence. Manipur is one such nation battling for self-determination. Manipur lost her independence on October 15, 1949. Since then, the Manipuris have been living as a colonised people. After annexation, Manipur's territory was dismembered and reduced to a lesser and smaller place. We forget that the Barak

Valley and the Ningthi Valley were once inside our borders. The Indian settlers are encroaching our land day by day. They now outnumber us. They have completely diluted Manipur's ethnic makeup. They threaten our original identity.

Before the advent of British colonial rule, our ancestors owned a vast area of land that extended beyond the boundary of what is now Manipur, as far as Barak valley and Ningthi Valley, and they coexisted peacefully with the hill-people. This chapter of our history is now hard to comprehend after Manipur was deprived of its rights during this short period of colonial rule. India's settlers have taken over Thangal Bazar, Minuthong, Mantripukri, Serou, Loktak project, Moreh and Jiribam. The hill areas such as Motbung, Kalapahar, Kangpokpi, Kanglatongbi etc are occupied by the non-Indian immigrant Nepalis exploiting the natural assets. The colonized native places are now increasingly appearing more alien to today's young generation. In the 1991 census the population of the Meiteis, including Pangals, did not reach 40% of the total population of Manipur. The Meiteis in Manipur are in danger of extinction, just as Cacharis are in Cachar and Tripuri in Tripura within a very short period of time. The flood of settlers has submerged Manipur up to her neck. If we remain indifferent and do not take action today, the Meiteis will face extinction within decades.

In spite of the fact that we have arrived at such a crucial moment in history, there are still many Meiteis who like to live dropping down on their knees in submission to the enemy. For their own benefit, they are selling the freedom of their motherland. To obtain a mere seat and position, they often kneel at the enemy's feet. Instead of uniting for the welfare of the people, they are killing each other for their own selfish gain. Their priority lies in stealing public funds and other acts of corruption. They impose Armed Forces Special Power Act. Under this Act, many innocents are being arrested and killed. They have defiled our sisters. The memories of the rape of Chanu Rose and Luingamla have left our sisters fearful for their lives.

Manipur is experiencing many incidents that have never occurred elsewhere in the world. In the Langjing and Oinam incidents, the enemy has violated human rights savagely. They treated our sisters like game animals. The massacre of Heirangoithong teaches us: "Who are our enemies?" To demonstrate their dominance, the Indian forces brutally killed many sons of the soil, including Ingudam Mangi, Jugindro Pibeya, and Biramani Heisnam. We still remember the brutal killing of Nabakumar, Chaobhal and Pramodini. Also today, the enemy continues to shoot dead young people at frisking-stops. There have also been many reports of deaths in their custody.

We have also heard many reports that the enemy works hand-in-hand with drug cartels and encourages our young generation to get addicted to drugs. There is no doubt that what the state and its forces are doing is exterminating the entire generation of youth. Unless we find the means to cope with them, the future devastation will be more horrific than the Seven Years Genocide.

Following in the footsteps of our ancestors, Hirachandra and Yumjaotaba, who raised a liberation guerrilla of brave Meiteis to defend their country, we must also stand united to defend against the forces that are leading us into a new devastation. We think it is better if there is no killing among us driven by egoistic motives from today onwards. We recall and honour the sacrifices made by our kings Gambhir Singh and Narasing in uniting the Meiteis in the Barak valley, liberating Manipur from the Burmese and achieving international recognition for Manipur as an independent state.

In commemoration of the liberation of Manipur from the Burmese, the Manipuri National Federation will launch a march with the pledge of “*Eikhoi Amuk Khuntaklaroi*” (“Genocide Never Again”). Our volunteers will march on foot from Imphal to Barak. We will ignite the flame of liberation at Chandrapur in Cachar (Barak valley). On January 9, the flame will be brought to Silchar for a public meeting commemorating the anniversary of *Chahi Taret Khuntakpa*. The flame will then be transported to Imphal, ignited in every village, and finally a mass meeting will be held at Mapal Kangjeibung. We invite everyone to attend the meeting.”

(Author's translation)

In the last paragraph of the pre-March circular the Manfederation declares, “We must not stop. Let us fight to defend our own culture and our nationhood. For once, we must live together as free people. Let us follow in the footsteps of our ancestors who sacrificed their lives for the sake of freedom.”

It is quite clear from the above quoted leaflet that the Barak Valley March of 1993 was a mobilisation of youth for a resurgent nationalist revolution. The Manipuri National Federation argued that India's policy on Manipur may lead to a new devastation in the future. They described the then prevailing situation using the historical analogy of the Burmese occupation of Manipur from 1819 to 1826.

If we take a step back and assess the contemporary history of Manipur from a wider perspective, some patterns begin to reveal themselves. What we can discern in all political

movements in Manipur is a pattern of rise and fall over time. We see a similar pattern here in the Manipuri National Federation's campaign as well, but the consequence is the bloodiest yet.

To pursue this anomaly is to seek insight into other similar events. A classic example is the first Manipuri nationalist revolutionary campaign taken up in 1953 by the Revolutionary Nationalist Party (RNP), which was abruptly nipped in the bud by a sedition case, the first of its kind in India after independence. We may gain some insight into historical dynamics by looking in more closely the history of Manipuri nationalism.

MANIPURI NATIONALISM AND ITS MODERN ROOTS

Manipuri nationalism as an ideology can be said to have originated in the mid-eighteen century. Manipur's quest for self-determination can be traced back to the mid-18th century when the Burmese expansionist activities began to threaten Manipur's sovereignty. Manipur's century-long struggles to gain independence from foreign dominance gave rise to a sense of nationhood. Burma conquered Manipur for 65 years, from 1760s to 1825 and the British controlled Manipur for 56 years from 1891 to 1947. While the modern idea of Manipuri nationalism originated in the late 1940s it has its genesis in 1947-49 when the British colonial rule ended and the India Dominion took direct control of Manipur. Before it was taken over by the Dominion of India on October 15, 1949, Manipur had a responsible government and a constitutional monarchy regulated by the Manipur State Constitution Act, 1947. The Act was the culmination of a long-cherished dream of the people of Manipur for self-rule and democracy. As a first step and direct response to the people's outcry for a responsible government in Manipur, King Chura Chand Singh (r. 1891-1941) proposed Manipur's first constitution in 1939. (Resistance September 21, 1976: 7) But the scheme did not materialize. (Ibid. 3 October 1976: 6) In a second attempt, the State Constitution of Manipur was drafted in 1947 at the initiative of his successor, King Bodh Chandra (r. 1941-1955). Manipur gained its independence at midnight intervening 14 and 15 August, 1947. Manipur became the first democracy in South Asia when the Manipur State Constitution Act, 1947 was passed on May 8, 1947 and the first Manipur State Assembly was convened on October 18, 1948, three years ahead of India.

But this remarkable 'forging of Manipuris into a people and transfer of power to the people within the framework of constitutional monarchy inevitably tending towards a Republic' had

taken a turn for the worse overnight when India annexed the kingdom in 1949 (Soyam 2013: 102). King Bodh Chandra, the constitutional head of the Manipur State, was held under house arrest when he visited Shillong, the capital of India's undivided province of Assam, to discuss Manipur-India relations. Also, in Imphal, the capital of Manipur, Indian forces surrounded the palace, seized telephone and telegraph lines, and isolated the Maharaja from his people.² Under duress, the Maharaja signed the 'Merger' Agreement, 1949 on September 21, 1949. The Maharaja ceded to the Dominion Government of India full and executive authority, jurisdiction, and power over the administration of the State. The first act of Democratic India following annexation was to smother democratic institutions and values. India converted Manipur into a Part C state, which was the lowest possible political status in India (Soyam 2013: 102). The Government of India on imposing the Chief Commissioner's rule over Manipur arbitrarily dissolved the democratically elected and popularly elected legislature and the Cabinet of the state without repealing the Manipur State Constitution Act, 1947 under which they were formed (Sadasivan 1963: 634). In response to this, a series of political movements demanding restoration of popular government in Manipur have emerged.

Manipuri nationalism at the very beginning was monarchical. King Bodh Chandra actively used nationalism to strengthen Manipur's independent status. He was very well aware that India constituted a serious danger for the independence of the kingdom. He realised that the threat to his reign and the independence of Manipur and was convinced that only a modern, democratic nation would be safe from a foreign take-over.³ So, he adopted a modern and democratic political system by passing the Manipur State Constitution Act, in 1947. The major challenge to Bodh Chandra's reign came from the Manipur State Congress party demanding integration of Manipur into India and also the communist's conspiracy for the abolition of monarchy, which they then perceived as a feudal institution.

Manipuri nationalism is a reaction against Indian domination functioning on the belief that Manipur should be independent. The entire fabric of Manipuri nationalism is based on the Manipur State Constitution Act, 1947 which means that all that is vital and good in Manipur

²Interview of Rani Khumalambam Kamini Devi, consort of Bodh Chandra, Mayengbam Anandamohon: A documentary film, DDK Imphal.

³Chamber of Princes, Cabin 6. File no 2 & 3. Secretariat Library, Imphal; Chamber of Princes files, ARC Library.

can be traced back to it. The Manipur State Constitution Act, 1947 became a symbolic signifier of freedom. Manipur has reached a high degree of exemplary expression in its struggle for the right of nations to self-determination, which is reflected both in its civil and armed movements that are all somehow rooted in this iconic law. The Act is much more than just a forgotten relic of the past; it is the foundation of all contemporary movements in Manipur encompassing aspects of self-determination movement, hill autonomy, inner line permit system, script, language movement, etc. It operates at the level of collective conscience of varied social and political movements. It can be considered as the master key of the said movements. The Manipur State Constitution Act of 1947 and its associated literature can be viewed as the national ideology of Manipur from an academic perspective. The Manipur State Constitution Act, 1947 has evolved gradually into a guiding principle capable of defending Manipur's national interests and its threatened identity. Over the past 70 years, the Act has served as a source of critique and inspiration in the trajectory of Manipuri nationalism.

Manipuri nationalism has its own historical lineage. Historically, the Manipur Praja Santi party, the ruling parties of independent Manipur (1947-1949), was the major force behind Manipuri nationalism. The Praja Santi was a royalist party. After the first election of 1948, the Praja Santi formed a coalition government with Manipur Krishak Sabha. Manipur Krishak Sabha was a party founded by the communist Hijam Irabot. The Manipur State Congress, an Indian nationalist party, failed to obtain power. In this period, Manipur can be viewed broadly through the lens of three political currents or trends: Manipuri nationalism, Communism, and Indian nationalism. Manipur Praja Santi Sova was formed to contest the Indian nationalists who were causing havoc in Manipur to make it part of India.

In recent years, academics and activists are attempting to paint a mythical picture of a founding father of Manipur nationalism. Their first major target is Hijam Irabot. Nevertheless, all original documents on his movements were clear and vivid. This raises even more questions. What is the motive behind creating Irabot as the sole founding father around 1960s and 1970s? What motivated nationalists to choose and handpick their founding fathers regardless of the history of Manipuri nationalism? Is there any motive that will strengthen their leadership? It is a bit cryptic. It deserves further study.

Here we would like to highlight the opinion of the communist leader Hijam Irabot himself on the merger issue. In the 19th issue of the *Anouba Yug*, published on August 12, 1947, there is a statement signed by Hijam Irabot, Bijoy Singh and Ibotombi Singh. The statement reads,

“Manipur would enter a new era on August 15, 1947. It is felt by many that there will also be a responsible government to maintain a good relationship between the state and its citizens. It is also heard that the people would hoist the tricolour flag of India, while the Maharaja of Manipur would hoist the state flag on the Independence Day. This has caused suspicion among the people about whether Manipur would also declare independence like Hyderabad State. If that is the case, the claim about Manipur joining India is a lie. If it is true, it does not make sense to celebrate the Independence Day. Some parts of Bharat (India) were ruled by native kings only so the British could oppress the people. It is direct attack against India. This will not be tolerated by the people of both India and the princely states. On the occasion of the Independence Day, August 15, 1947, we demand the following: -

- 1) Manipur should be merged with India.
- 2) There should be a responsible government in Manipur.
- 3) There should be a reduction in land revenue tax.
- 4) Manipur should provide cultivable land to its peasants.
- 5) Abolition of foreigner (Indian and other non-Manipuri) passport system.”

(Author's translation)

The decision did not mean that Irabot accepted the complete integration of Manipur with India along the lines of the Congress party. He had another idea of Manipur. In contrast to the above statement, the election pamphlet issued by the Manipur Praja Santi Sova on June 7, 1948 clearly shows the agenda of the party, “.... the Praja Santi Sova was formed with the blessing of the Chief Minister Maharaj Kumar Priyabrata after deliberation for four days by people from all corners....In case the Congress and its factions are returned with a majority in the Assembly, they may join together to enact a law to sell Manipur to India.”

It now makes clear that there were also a few people who opposed the merger, whose names disappear entirely. The Manipur Praja Sova party was established by Ibotombi, an ex-Sub Inspector of Police, on November 10, 1947 with the support of Maharaja Bodh Chandra and Maharaj Kumar Priyabrata. (Sanajaoba 2005: 285-85; Resistance March 7. 1978: 6) The Manipur Praja Santi Sova was born out of a non-political group called Manipur Praja, during

the fratricidal *satyagraha* between two factions of the pro-merger party Manipur State Congress - Tomal Congress and Tompok Congress. (Resistance Feb 28 1978: 6). The Manipur State Assembly elections becoming a reality led to its transformation into a political party. The party was known sometimes called as *Ningthou Khanba*, meaning king-maker or king follower, since it was monarchical. (Assembly Proceeding 1972: 82)

Talking about the political underpinnings of the Praja Santi, Sadasivan is very clear about this:

“... when the British withdrew from the sub-continent, in their state of helplessness some of them (monarchies) hurriedly sought a contrivance in political parties to retain their losing power. The Praja Santi Party (Subjects’ Peace or Welfare Party) Manipur was embodied with this end in view. The Manipur Constitutional Act 1947 envisaged a parliamentary democracy with a limited monarchy for the state. The royal family then favoured the formation of the Praja Santi Party because the securance of a docile parliamentary majority was necessary to unite in the constitutional monarch the real power. It so happened in 1947, when to the chagrin of the Congress Party torn by internal strife, the younger brother of the Maharaja, Priyabrata Singh who was then the leader of the Praja Santi Party formed the first popular Cabinet in the state” (1963: 139).

The transformation of Praja Santi Sova into a mass-based organisation can be seen following the annexation of Manipur in 1949. On March 23, 1949, Nongthonbam Ibomcha Singh, General Secretary of Manipur Praja Santi Sova sent a memorandum to the Governor of Assam, copied to the Prime Minister of India, opposing the merger of Manipur into India.

“Hearing something about the integration or merging of Manipur State, we, the Praja Santi party (Govt. party), on behalf of the people of Manipur State, have the honour to state that almost cent per cent of the people of the State are quite against the integration or merging on account of the following: -

1. The present relation between India and the Manipur State is most satisfactory and politic both for India and Manipur. (*sic*) On account of the geographical position, Manipur is of strategic importance and is now standing as a helping pillar for defence against Burmah, our traditional enemy, because Manipuris are quite satisfied with the present relationship.
2. Even if all the States of India have been merged, Manipur State ought to be tolerated as an exception, because the language and the customs of Manipur are quite different from any part of India.

3. As Manipuris are backward in every respect, we shall not be able to run parallel with other peoples. We know that exploitation will never be the intention of India Government; but circumstances will cause exploitation.
4. That almost cent per cent of the Manipuris are against integration or merging will be clear from a proper referendum.
5. Economically, politically and socially, Manipur can self-sustain as Manipur has necessary relations with India regarding defence, communication and external affairs. The present political and cordial relation between India and Manipur is quite to be hankered after by any searching politician. That how do we respect and obey the Indian leaders or rulers will be clear from the opinion of the Indian leaders who had or have been here.
6. The income and the resource of Manipur is quite satisfactory. The income of the present year will be nearly thirty lakhs of rupees of other parts of India; because valuation of economic goods is quite different. (*sic*)

The following resolutions was passed at a meeting of Praja Santi Sova's MLAs on August 25, 1949, under the presidency of Khaidem Iboton Singh, President, Praja Santi Sova

- 1) That the good and cordial relations between India and Manipur State under the Instrument of Accession be continued for some years for the interest and safeguard of Manipur and India.
- 2) That the Home Rule of the Manipur State be run by the local figures under democratic constitution to allow of self-development with a keen sense of responsibility, economically, politically and socially and that the representative of India, if there should be any, in Manipur State, be bound by the Constitution without interference to day-to-day internal administration except when required constitutionally.

The resolution was forwarded to the Prime Minister of India, the Deputy Prime Minister of India, the Governor of Assam and the Dewan (Representative of India in Manipur). (Resistance, September 11, 1979: 6)

Since it was monarchical, the Manipur Praja Santi Party had no popular backing (Maipaksana: 1950). A need was felt for a mass-based organisation to mobilise public opinion against India's annexation of Manipur. Priyabrata recalls, in an interview with Kailash S Aggarwal and R.K. Ranjan, about the absence of support by the people,

“Well, after the merger, Major Khathing, my good friend, beseeched me ‘Let’s go underground (to fight against the merger).’ But I coolly told him: “See you are married! You have a wife and children to look after. I have none. It is easier for me that way. But then we must have followers – and we don’t have people behind us” (Singh 2017: 520).

In 1951, a new party called the All-Manipur National Union (AMNU) under the leadership of Sagolsem Indramani Singh, Nilamani Singh and Yangmaso Tangkhul took form with a better base of support than the Praja Santi Party, in order to express the popular reaction. (Sadasivan 1963) The party was established on August 5, 1951.⁴ The party argued that Manipuris have a separate nationality and demanded that Manipur be an independent state. Its immediate objective was to regain the constitutional government it enjoyed just before it was annexed to India. The party, therefore, received the liberal patronage of the members of the royal family, so that during the first general election of India, 1951-52,⁵ the sister of the Maharaja of Manipur, Binodini Devi, stood as the party’s most prominent candidate. The party's accord with the former ruling family led to the popular surmise that it was actually a royalist group seeking to gather the masses for the Manipur Praja Santi Party. In spite of this, the All-Manipur National Union was a unique and different organization and was zealously devoted to the shibboleth “Manipur for Manipuris” (Sadasivan 1963: 167). From January 1, 1953, the party published a daily newspaper called “Mother Manipur”. According to a report dated April 29, 1953 from S. Palit, Superintendent of Police, Manipur, AMNU published articles very often ‘against non-Manipuri government servants working in Manipur and spreading class hatred between Manipuris and non-Manipuris.’⁶ Wahengbam Pralhad Singh was the editor of this paper. On April 18, 1953, an article published in the said newspaper writes,

⁴Ministry of States, Political A section, Secret, 1953, Nos. 11(15)-PA/53, National Archive (NAI), India.

⁵ India adopted a democratic republican form of government in 1950 with a written constitution. It held its first general elections, on the basis of adult suffrage, from October 1951 to February 1952. The Constitution of India provides both for direct and indirect elections. The people elected directly 489 members to the House of the People or the Lower House of the Parliament, 3,279 members to State Assemblies and 90 members to Electoral Colleges. For the election to the House of the People two seats were allotted for Manipur and for the Electoral Colleges thirty seats were allotted. Election to the Council of States was combined with Tripura by rotation.

⁶Ministry of States, Political A section, Secret, 1953, Nos. 11(15)-PA/53 NAI

“If the Indian Government does not pay heed to our request in demanding Responsible Government, we, having separated from the Indian Federation according to rules laid down may try so that Manipur may become a Buffer State. The U.N.O. also may consider our request”
(*sic*)

In 1953, the Praja Santi Party, the All-Manipur National Union, Gandhi Sevok Sabha and Communist Party formed the Democratic Front in order to create agitation for the restoration of responsible government, which had been unconstitutionally abolished. In response to the Front's growing momentum, the Indian Congress Party intervened and subdued it(Sadasivan 1963: 115).

On or around April 18, 1953, the All-Manipur National Union merged with the Gandhi Sevok Sabha and formed a new party called the Revolutionary Nationalist Party. Rajkumar Maipaksana, secretary of Gandhi Sevok Sabha, served as General Secretary. Yangmaso Shaiza served as president.⁷ The Manipur State Communist Party had refused collaboration with the RNP on the ground that the RNP's move was sectarian.⁸

Sagolsem Indramani, Yangmaso and Maipaksana published three pamphlets asking the people to attend the meeting to be held at Pologround on April 19, 1953. The meeting was attended by a large number of people. The meeting was presided over by a hill man, Angara Anal. The meeting was addressed by Indramani, Maipaksana, Yangmaso Tangkhul and Bacha Singh. The Times of India reports the event as thus,

A 10,000 strong public meeting threatened here yesterday to support the move for an independent Manipur State if the Union Government did not heed the demand for a popular Ministry for Manipur. The meeting unanimously passed a resolution asking the Government to give Manipur a popular Ministry chosen by the members of the Electoral College. If the demand was not met with, 'the meeting decided to support fully the movement the Revolutionary Nationalist Party proposed to launch for an independent Manipur. The meeting was held at the Polo ground under the auspices of the Revolutionary

⁷Ibid.

⁸Ibid.

Nationalist Party, which was recently formed by the amalgamation of the All-Manipur National Union and the Gandhi Sevak Sabha. (“Ultimatum to Centre” April 21, 1953)

In his letter to V. Viswanathan, Joint Secretary to the GOI, dated May 5, 1953 R.R. Bhargava, the Chief Commissioner of Manipur, wrote that Maharaja Bodh Chandra, Maharajkumar Priyabrata and their royalist group were suspected of being behind this move.

“The Party is led by Sagolsem Indramani Singh who used to be a spy of Maharajkumar Priyabrata Singh, brother of the Maharajah and Chief Minister of this State on the date of its integration. Indramani is still believed to be a man of the Maharajah and his brother Priyabrata Singh. The Police suspect that the Revolutionary Nationalist Party is financed by the Maharajah, who still retains the illusion of regaining his State and has been encouraged by the recent happenings in the Naga Hills. It is widely talked of here and is also borne out by secret Police reports that the Maharajah contributed a sum of Rs 3000/- to the Party fund some days before its meeting of the 19th April, for carrying on propaganda for the buffer State cause... Indramani Singh was seen coming out of the Palace at 9 PM on the day of the meeting after seeing P.B Singh, brother of the Maharajah.” The letter then continued, “Besides Indramani Singh, the other leading lights in the party are Yangmaso, a graduate Tangkhul Naga and brother of Lungshim, Aide-de-camp of the Maharaja.... The Police suspect that the Maharajah has active sympathies if not indirectly association with the Naga National Council (NNC) of Zapho Phizo. The fact that he has kept in his service as his Aide-de-Camp Lungshim Tangkhul suspected to be a worker of the Naga National Council (NNC) lends support to this suspicion. Lungshim, it is reported, is engaged to Miss Ranu, niece of Phizo and a worker of the Naga National Council (NNC). There is definite proof that Lungshim acted as the liaison between Trumbull, New York Times correspondent and the Kohima Nagas at Imphal in the evening of the 27th March, prior to the Prime Minister’s last visit to Imphal on the 28th. The propaganda that is carried on here by the Party has a family likeness with the Naga National Council’s propaganda at Kohima. There is all the talk about a buffer State and of a reference to the U.N.O., if necessary for achieving the cause. Manipuris are mentioned as a people separate from the Indians.”⁹

⁹Ibid.

On April 24, the four leaders of the party, Indramani, Yangmaso, Maipaksana and Wahengbam Pralhada Singh were arrested and convicted under Section 124 A. 153A I.P.C and sentenced to 6 months imprisonment by the sub-divisional Magistrate, Sadar on September, 12 1953. They were charged with organising meetings and distribution of leaflets for an independent, sovereign, buffer State of Manipur.

On April 27, 1953 the four leaders sent a memorandum to Pandit Nehru, Prime Minister of India through the Superintendent Jail.

As your love of India is above every other consideration, our love for Manipur is also above every other consideration, when you think Indian as an equal with the Britishers, we Manipuris hold the same view that we are not less equal in any respect with your Indians. In the name of universal brotherhood and equality of all the different" races of India, you have won the Independence of India and today you are saddled on the throne of Delhi, charged with the responsibility of looking after the welfare of every nationality which make up your proud India. But your Independence of India has lost its meaningas regards to Manipur, we are today subjected as a slave people and all our voice for a change has our gone unheeded. At time when you could not endure the rule of another -people over you, how do you expect us to remain under the rule of the heartless rogues.¹⁰

The fall of RNP marked the end of the first phase of Manipuri nationalist movement. There were two ideas of independent Manipur that emerged during the first phase of Manipuri nationalism. Firstly, that Manipur should remain independent with its constitutional monarchy, and the Manipur-India relationship must only be maintained by the Instrument of Accession, as advocated by the Praja Santi. Secondly, Hijam Irabot's vision of a socialist autonomous republic of Manipur¹¹ within a socialist India, free from imperialism, feudalism and capitalism. In his peasant and other socio-political reformation movements, Hijam Irabot also displayed certain characteristics of nationalism within a communist framework.

¹⁰Ibid.

¹¹Possibly as in the case of Byelorussian SSR or Ukraine in USSR and Kosovo in SFR Yugoslavia.

A NEW PHASE OF MANIPURI NATIONALISM

In the 1960s, the Manipuri nationalist movement was reignited. In this phase the movement entered its revolutionary period with the foundation of the Meitei State Committee and the United National Liberation Front (UNLF). There emerged the revolutionary struggle to establish a sovereign socialist Manipur. For the first time, the nationalists called for a sovereign Manipur rather than independence or autonomy. Several armed groups have emerged since the 1960s, along with their overground organisations.

The Pan-Manipuri Youth League (PANMYL) was one such overground organization that stood up boldly. Founded in 1968, PANMYL was the result of the efforts of the generation that reached their young adulthood in the 1960s. They were mostly well educated, mostly graduates from Indian universities (Parratt 2005: 136). They were the first generation of Manipuri youth to experience ‘oppressive Indian rule’. (*Bharat-ki-Loilam*, 1993: vii) *Naharol*, meaning youth in Meiteirol, began to be used as the synonym of a nationalist from this generation onwards. PANMYL describes itself as follows,

“Pan Manipuri Youth League (PANMYL) was a social and political organisation founded in 1968 with a revolutionary commitment to awakening the Manipuris from the slumber of colonial rule. It revived, restored and in fact, rewrote the glorious history of Manipur which was made forgotten, distorted and relegated to insignificance by the colonial masters beginning with the British. Pan Manipuri Youth League successfully rehoused a pride in everybody born as a Manipuri in this hilly state” (Chandramani 1970).

On December 28, 1968, PANMYL took shape at Students Day Home, Gauhati University. During a three-day meeting from 20 to 22 June 1969, the PANMYL was constituted and its functionaries elected at MDU Hall, Imphal. (*Bharat-ki-Loiram* 1993: vii) The *Lamyamba* (first published on August 3, 1969) and the *Resistance* (first published on January 9, 1976) were the two organs of PANMYL. About their two organs PANMYL writes,

PANMYL's mouthpiece *Lamyamba* (Pioneer), a monthly published in local vernacular and the *Resistance*, a weekly published in English, came heavily against the state and its misrule. It took corruption as a vice born and bred by the colonial system. Both the journals were engaged in a strong anti-corruption drive exposing ministers, offices and politicians through their far reading

investigations. Agonies suffered by the people in the hills specially at the hands of the Indian army were brought into public. Rape cases and excesses perpetrated by the Indian army in the interior hill areas were investigated and brought into public for justice. (Chandramani 1970)

The repressive policies of government against PANMYL hindered the organisation's activity. For instance, PANMYL leaders and members Prof. Kh Ibomcha, Prof. O Bhogendra, Prof Y. Tikendra, Prof Th. Ibotombi, Prof Nandalal Sharma, O. Natum, Ch Ibohal and Achou Toijamba were arrested in December 1970-January 1971 and were detained in the Manipur Central Jail under the Orissa Preventive Detention Act. 1970. (*Lamyamba* April 1971 :20-26) Conflicts within the leadership also contributed to its inactivity. According to a former member, PANMYL was aimed at inspiring the youth to spark a revolution, and it succeeded in accomplishing that mission.

MANIPURI NATIONAL FEDERATION

Following the dormancy of PANMYL, Achou Toijamba, a leader of the organization, founded the Manipuri National Federation in the late 1980s. He was a master organizer during the Pan-Manipuri days (Yambem 2015). Manfederation took shape on January 9, 1988 at new Palace's Hijagang in Imphal. (A. Waikhom, interview, March 5, 2022). The Kangla Lanpung, a monthly journal in Meiteirol, was the only organ of Manfederation. Rajkumar Sanatomba, better known by his pseudonym KonungSanatomba, was the editor of the journal.

In its early stage, Manfederation led the agitation for the removal of the Assam Rifles, a central paramilitary force, from the Kangla, the old seat of power of Manipur. As part of the agitation a conglomerate called *Kangla Kanba Lup* (KKL) comprising of Manfederation, People's Movement Committee under the leadership of Rajkumar Ranendrajit, People's Democratic Movement led by Dr. L. Pardesi, Poramlen Apunba led by Sapamcha Jadumani, and All Manipur Students' Union (AMSU) was formed. As a result of the agitation Kangla was opened to the public in August 1992 (Devi 1998: 163).

Manfederation and its organ the Kangla Lanpung were quite popular in 1990-1993, as evidenced by certain Manipuri words we use today. For instance, *senmitlon* for economy, *manabakhunai* for egalitarian society, *tangdu-leitadaba* for chaos etc. were coined by Manfederation.

The next initiative of Manfederation focused on nationalist mobilization of urban and suburban youth. As part of the month-long commemoration of the liberation war against Burmese occupation, a long march from Imphal to the Barak Valley in Assam with the slogan

"*Eikhoiamukkhuntaklaroi*" took place in January 1993. This long-march brought together 200 young marchers and 200 volunteers. The march was officially known as "*Barak Tampak-ki Khongchat*".

The commemoration of January 9 was not the first time. Gambhir Singh, one of the founders of modern Manipur, died on January 9, 1834. PANMYL chose this date in 1975 to commemorate Manipur's liberation. Here we can flash back to what happened on January 9, 1976 to gain a deep understanding of the Barak march of 1993. The Pan-Manipuri Youth League first commemorated January 9 as "National Liberation Day". We found a photograph of the League leader Achou Toijamba giving a speech on this function with a huge red flag of Pan-Manipuri youth league in the background and volunteers standing with red flags. Now it will be more appropriate to call this flag as the Manipuri nationalist flag. The motif of golden ouroboros Pakhangba has become a symbol of Manipuri nationalism. The golden ouroboros Pakhangba motif against a maroon background was first hoisted in Ukhrul as the Manipur State flag in the late 1930s, which was commissioned by MK Priyabrata (Singh 2017: 48). Second, it was hoisted as Manipur independent flag at Kangla and Manipur State Durbar Hall when the British left Manipur in 1947. It was in use officially by independent Manipur till 1949. Since the annexation, it has become a symbol of Manipuri nationalism. The National Liberation Day function of 1976 was clearly recorded in the Resistance, the mouthpiece of Pan-Manipuri Youth League:

"The function was performed in commemoration of the liberation of Manipur from the Burmese one hundred and fifty years ago. It was Gambhir Singh who led the liberation forces – the famous Manipur Levy – in 1826 from Cachar and again became the king of Manipur with Langthabal as the new capital. He died on 9th January 1834 and was cremated at a spot near his palace. Incidentally, this day coincided with the transfer of Kabaw Valley to Burma. The procession started at 1105 hrs., five minutes behind schedule. As the procession moved on the volunteers shouted slogans and marched vigorously to the tune of a patriotic song played on the mike. An attraction for the onlookers was the one hundred and fifty-one flags carried by the processionists to mark an equal number of anniversary days that have elapsed since the Liberation. The red flags bearing the *Pakhangba Paphal* and *Kai* emblem of the League proudly fluttered under the clear winter sky. Each of the thousand- strong processionists also wore the League's red armband on their left arms.... At Lanthabal, the processionists formed a rectangle round the tomb of Gambhir Singh. Wreaths were then placed at the tombs by Okendrajit, ex-Ruler of Manipur, followed by Okram Joy, the local M.L.A, and the President of the League. The Chief Minister Rajkumar Dorendra could not join the ceremony as he reached Imphal the same morning from Delhi. The flag-bearers, in the front row of the human rectangle, dipped their flags when all those present observed one

minute's silence to pay homage to the resistance fighters who had laid down their lives in the liberation struggle.

The last in the ceremony was the oath taken by the volunteers en masse that they also would dedicate their lives for the motherland. With the old deserted palace of Gambhir Singh as a backdrop, the grim faces of the volunteers were matched by the solemnity of the whole ceremony." (*Resistance* January 20 1976: 7)

A few days ahead of the Barak March of 1993, Manfederation released an audio cassette titled "*Pullasi Eikhoi Hayengidamak*". The cassette contains seven nationalist and progressive songs – '*Lamyamba Meitei* (Pioneer Meitei), *Pullasi eikhoi* (Let us be united), *Chatlu Chatlu* (We march), *Ariba puwarigi anouba yawolda*, (Our history for the new revolution), *Lamyallo Meitei Pakhang* (Lead the path of new revolution), *Sangbannaba chingyada*, (on the sloped vale of green hills) and *Ting-ting chaoro* (Let your life-force grow). Additionally, there was a short introductory message of 0.34 minutes delivered by Ningthouja Lancha, who led the Barak Valley March. The message says,

"In this time of disintegration, we stand together for the next generation. Now the time has come to solidify our way together to create a new history. With this thought we offer the album "*Pullasi Eikhoi Hayengidamak*" (Let us unit together for better tomorrow) in remembrance of our forefathers who stood on the battlefield and fought against the Burmese to safeguard our independence."

(Author's translation)

All the seven songs were written by Achou Toijamba (Mayambi, interview, April 17, 2022). The songs were played throughout the valley on loudspeaker during the mobilization of the volunteers. The songs were not written all at once. These were the songs sung in the previous movements. For instance, the song *Lamyallo Meitei Pakhang* (*Lamyallo* (Lead the path of new revolution) and *Ting Tingchaoro* were the rally song of the first Barak March of 1974 organised by the Lamyamba Meitei Pakhang, a wing of PANMYL and in the peasants' movements, *Sangbanaba Chingyada* was sung. The 1992 re-collected version of these songs was sung by RK Jotika, Devola, Tikendra, Lancha and others. The songs were recorded at Kaypee Studio at Kwakeithel, Imphal.

In the last week of December, 1992, 200 volunteers were registered. They came from almost every part of the Manipur valley, from Pallel village in the east to Sanasabi village in the north. Altogether 200 marchers, 100 male and 100 female volunteers took part in the Barak march (*Kangla Lanprung*, 1993: 39). A total of 400 people participated in this march. But it is

hard to get to know all the names of 400 persons. Unfortunately, all the office documents of Manfederation have never been discovered and were mostly likely burned. It is said that the video footages and films of the march were picked up by unknown armed assailants. Such files and footage became easy source for them to target their victims (L, Ningthouja, interview, 17 March 2022).

The entourage went from one Meitei village to another. They gave lectures on the three main objectives of the federation – consolidation, economic self-development and self-government.

They used words such as *seipham* for small meeting places and *ingkhhol* for AchouToijamba's homestead or main gathering place at Palace compound Thangapat.

The gathering of the marchers in the headquarter of Manfederation at Thangapat started from 31 December 1992. On January 2, 1993, the Barak Valley March was flagged off by Rajkumar Priyogopalsana from the Statehood Square in Imphal¹². In his speech at the flag-off ceremony, Rajkumar Priyogopalsana addressed to the marchers as "*pathoucha*." Priyogopalsana was the patriarch of the Manipuri dance and a pioneer nationalist as well. Thounaojam Iboyaima also attended the flag-off ceremony. The marchers were grouped into marchers, volunteers, team leaders and medical team. Ningthouja Lancha led the whole march as *lanchingpurel*. The team leaders and volunteers wore red shirts with head scarves printed with the Khamenchatpa motif. In addition, they wore an armband with a yellow Pakhangba on black. The marchers wore grey shirts with black head scarves. They also fluttered the nationalist red flag bearing Pakhangba and a black flag with the same motif.

The marchers set out on foot from the Statehood Square, and carried on towards New Cachar road – Keithelmanbi (21.3 km) – Tupul (47.4 km) – Noney (59.4 km)– Irang (92.1 km) – Kaimai (159 km) - Jiribam (206 km) – Chandrapur (Assam, 239 km), where *ningtam meira* (lit., torch of liberation) was lighted at the old palace site of King Gambhir Singh. The message of consolidation was carried to every Meitei village of the Barak valley. Among them may be named Itkhola, Sonarbond, Udharbond, Rongpur, Karaikandi, Banskandi, Ranipur, Tolenpur and Lakhimpur. A large number of inspired Meiteis from these villages also joined the march. On the January 9, the commemoration of *Chahi taret khuntakpa* under the theme *eikhoi amuk khuntaklalo* was held at Silchar Gandhi Park (19 km from Chandrapur). The function was graced by Maharajkumar Priyabrata. With the 'liberation torch' from Chandrapur, the

¹²The present-day parking space behind the Polo Ground, Imphal.

marchers returned back to Imphal via Tongjei Maril road (old Cachar road). On their way, the volunteers made a detour to Nungkao village (112 km from Silchar), where they met Rani Gaidinliu and received her blessings. Then they marched through Khoupum village (65.2 km from Nungkao) to reach Imphal from Nungkao. On January 19, the flame of liberation reached the Imphal valley at Lamangdong (53 km from Khoupum). They lit the flame as they marched through Moirang, Thangalawai, Keirenphabi, Kumbi, Churachandpur, Kakching, KakchingKhunou, Umathel, Elangkhampokpi, Pallel, Sugnu, Thoubal, Yairipok, Andro, Keibi, Lamlai, Sekmai, Lamsang, Nambol, Wangoo, and Khurai villages. (Kangla Lanpung 1993). On January 21, the marchers stayed a night at Wangjing village. (*Hueiyen Lanpao* 23 January 1993:1). Finally, on January 31, the marchers reached Kangla and lit the flame of liberation there. A confrontation between the marchers and the police occurred when the marchers were refused entry to Kangla. In protest, the marchers blocked the way of the Governor's car as he approached the western gate of Kangla. It resulted in Imphal clamping down on Section 144 CRPC. The closing function was held at Mapal Kangjeibung (Polo Ground). Ahanthem Nilamani, who graced the event, made a speech in which he said that the tears the marchers shed on the day represented the tears of colonised people longing for liberation.

In the months following the Barak March, members and volunteers of Manfederation were attacked without warning. Konung Sanatomba, editor of Kangla Lanpung, was shot dead by unknown assailants on June 30 at Brahmapur Lalji Lakpa Leikai in Imphal (*Khollao* 1 July 1993: 1). Konung Sanatomba was also the nephew of MK Priyabrata. In 1993-1994 front pages were filled with news about bullet-riddled dead bodies found with signs of torture. Some were found with their eyes and mouths blindfolded and their hands tied behind. Several of them belonged to Manfederation. Although the organization continued to operate in the Cachar District of Assam for a few months, the bloodshed led to its inactivation in 1994. The activities of the Manfederation were suppressed in plain sight without warning and in the most violent manner, unlike the previous nationalist movements.

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